

UNIVERSITÀ
DI TRENTO

GUIDELINES FOR THE EDITORIAL ACTIVITY AND THE SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS OFFICE OF THE UNIVERSITY OF TRENTO

**GUIDELINES FOR THE EDITORIAL ACTIVITY AND THE SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS OFFICE
OF THE UNIVERSITY OF TRENTO**

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1. PREAMBLE AND DEFINITIONS

For the purposes of this document, “University’s editorial activity” refers to the publishing of intellectual works for which the University of Trento (hereinafter: UniTrento) acts as publisher or co-publisher.

UniTrento’s editorial activity does not pertain to a legal entity separate from the University. However, in certain regulatory contexts (University Open Science Policy) or informative ones (University webpages, Service Desk portal), the terms “Publishing House of the University of Trento” and “University Press” are used to refer to the University in its specific function as a publishing house.

UniTrento’s editorial activity was formally initiated in 1992. Since then, the University has been providing specific services for continuous editorial initiatives (journals and book series) or individual ones (single books) within its Structures (Departments, Centres, Directorates). With the aim of coordinating these services, in 2012 UniTrento centralized its technical-administrative staff that was primarily involved in supporting the editorial initiatives, and in 2021 the Scientific Publications Office (hereinafter: the Office) was established within the Dissemination and Evaluation of Research Outputs Division, part of the Directorate of Research Services and Valorization.

2. CURRENT ORGANIZATION OF THE UNIVERSITY’S EDITORIAL ACTIVITY

The Rector, as UniTrento’s legal representative, is the owner and responsible for the University’s editorial activity. In exercising this function, the Rector is required to update – personally or by delegation – the information communicated by UniTrento to the Register of Communication Operators (ROC), notifying the start of new journals, as well as changes to the identification data or the Editor-in-Chief of already-existing journals; the Rector is also required to communicate to the Court of Trento any changes in the management or identification data of journals registered with it.

The University Structures decide on the start of new editorial initiatives, upon request by an affiliated person, and guarantee their content and formal quality, as well as their economic sustainability. For initiatives falling within the types of works admitted for publication with UniTrento (detailed in paragraph 3.1), the Structures can request their inclusion in the University’s editorial activity, relying on the Office’s support and coordination. Each editorial initiative is under the responsibility of the Structure that decided on its launch. Each continuous initiative includes a Director / Editor-in-Chief (responsible to the publisher), a Scientific Committee (responsible

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for the criteria for selecting publication proposals and for the scientific assessment of proposals through peer review), and an Editorial Team (responsible for preparing the works for publication).

The Office centrally supports and coordinates the University's editorial activity from a technical-administrative point of view. It provides support and consultancy to proposers of new initiatives and to already-active editorial initiatives, and supports the Rector in exercising their function as publisher (preparing documentation for communications to the ROC and the Court, as well as fulfilling the legal deposit obligation).

3. UNITRENTO PUBLISHING POLICIES

3.1. Works Eligible for Publication

The types of works admitted by UniTrento as part of its editorial activity are **journals** and **books** of scientific relevance, of high didactic value, or pertaining to the so-called "third mission." The works published by UniTrento shall always include at least one text authored by a person affiliated with the University. The criteria for selecting publication proposals are established autonomously by each journal and book series published by UniTrento. To be admitted for publication, works shall undergo peer review or other types of quality assessment of their content, and be consistent with the editorial guidelines chosen by the relevant editorial initiative. The fulfillment of these requirements is guaranteed to the publisher by the Director / Editor-in-Chief of the specific editorial initiative and/or by the Structure proposing its publication.

3.2. Start of New Editorial Initiatives

The start of a new editorial initiative shall be requested by a person affiliated with the University. In the case of journals and book series, the characteristics of the initiative are communicated, via a specific form (*Scheda dell'iniziativa editoriale*), to the relevant Structure, which approves its start through a resolution. In the case of single books, only the approval of the person directing the Structure is required. The approving persons vouch for the content and formal quality of the initiative and the securing of the economic and human resources that are necessary for it.

The inclusion of an initiative in the University's publishing activity shall be requested from the Office by the proposer, through a specific procedure available on the Service Desk portal. Journals and informative

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periodicals are registered with the ROC; the registration of journals with the competent Court is reserved only for the ones that are published also in print edition, and is subject to the Rector's prior consent.

3.3. Persons Eligible for Publication

Each continuous editorial initiative published by UniTrento autonomously establishes which persons are admitted for publishing their works in it. Also authors and volume editors not affiliated with the University are admitted for the publication of single works (provided that the publication includes at least one contribution from a person affiliated with the University, as prescribed in paragraph 3.1). In any case, the publication proposal shall be submitted to the Office by a person affiliated with the University.

3.4. Open Access to Scientific Publications

In accordance with the University Open Science Policy approved by the Academic Senate on 7th December 2022, UniTrento promotes Diamond Open Access by publishing its works as digital editions on online platforms that comply with the standards and protocols for open access. The publication of a work in print edition is subject to its publication as an open access digital edition. Informative and institutional periodicals are not published on open access platforms.

3.5. Publishing Platforms for Open Access Digital Editions

UniTrento's scientific and didactic journals are published as digital editions on TESeO - Trento Editions Service for Open Science (<https://teseo.unitn.it>), a platform based on the open-source OJS software. The Office manages the website, which is reserved for the University's editorial activity; the publication of each issue is the responsibility of the journal's Editorial Team.

The digital editions of books published by UniTrento are available on IRIS UniTrento (<https://iris.unitn.it>), the University's institutional repository; the publication of each work is handled by the Office and shall be requested by the relevant Editorial Team through a specific procedure available on the Service Desk portal. Exceptions apply to book series published on OJS software before 2021 and subsequently included in TESeO, which may continue to publish their works in TESeO.

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3.6. Bibliographic Identification Codes

UniTrento guarantees the assignment of appropriate bibliographic identification codes to all publications falling within the University's editorial activity.

ISBN (International Standard Book Number) codes are assigned by the Office to each book and monographic journal issue. ISBNs are assigned when the works are ready for publication.

ISSN (International Standard Serial Number) codes are assigned, through the Office, to each journal and book series. The timing, methods, and requirements for the issuance of ISSNs are established by the sole Italian provider (Centro Italiano ISSN).

DOI (Digital Object Identifier) codes are assigned to each book, journal issue, and journal article. DOIs are assigned upon publication.

3.7. Copyright and License to Publish

The publication of a work by UniTrento is possible only with explicit authorizations issued by all parties holding economic rights over the texts and images contained therein. By filling in a specific license to publish form – which the Office makes available in advance to all editorial initiatives via the Service Desk portal –, each interested party grants the said authorization to UniTrento without time limits nor charges to the publisher, allowing the digital edition to be published under a Creative Commons license (UniTrento recommends using the Creative Commons - Attribution - Share-Alike license in its latest available version) and retaining the rights to their work (which may therefore be republished in other publishing venues, provided that the terms of the selected Creative Commons license are respected). The task of collecting the forms signed by the rights holders, verifying their completeness and correctness, and permanently archiving them on behalf of the publisher falls on the initiative's Editorial Team, under the responsibility of the person directing the initiative itself. UniTrento entirely defers to the authors or volume editors the voluntary submission of their works to the Italian General Public Register of Protected Works.

3.8. Scientific, Ethical, and Legal Responsibility of the Editorial Initiatives

Each editorial initiative is responsible to the publisher for:

- the content and formal quality of the works (as per paragraph 3.1), including the necessary peer assessment through the correct and scrupulous application of scientific review procedures, or through

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specific consultations in the case of works of high didactic value or pertaining to the so-called “third mission”;

- full compliance with copyright, through the collection and permanent conservation of the license to publish forms (as per paragraph 3.7) in accordance with the provisions of the University;
- full application of University regulations relating to research ethics and integrity, personal data protection and the processing of sensitive and judicial data, in addition to the obligation for journals to adopt a binding and publicly accessible code of ethics (or, alternatively, to state explicitly their adherence to the recommendations of COPE - Committee on Publication Ethics);
- timely provision of materials and information necessary for the publisher to fulfill legal obligations (e.g., communication of changes to the Editor-in-Chief or identification data of editorial initiatives, submission of print publications for legal deposit);
- the requirement of affiliation with a UniTrento Structure for the Editorial Team members with roles of responsibility towards the Office (the Editorial Team contact person and the technical contact person).

These guarantees are formally required by the publisher during the procedure for starting a new editorial initiative and/or during the procedure for requesting the publication of individual works.

The persons that are directly responsible to the publisher regarding the above-mentioned aspects are:

- in the case of journals, the Editor-in-Chief (*direttore responsabile*), a professional figure regulated by Italian Law no. 47 of 8th February 1948, and therefore also legally accountable;
- in the case of book series, the Director of the initiative;
- in the case of single books, its proposer, and the Director of the relevant Structure limited to the scientific value of the work.

UniTrento reserves the right to suspend online access to already published works, without the need for authorization from the relevant editorial initiative, in cases where evidence of the initiative’s failure to comply with its scientific, ethical, and legal responsibilities towards the publisher is found or reported by third parties.

UniTrento may also order the partial or total obscuring of an editorial initiative’s website in cases of serious infringements of University regulations or in cases where the legal requirements for a journal’s Editor-in-Chief cease to be met (e.g., being a licensed journalist enrolled in a professional register).

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3.9. Publication Costs Borne by the Editorial Initiatives

Costs related to a single editorial initiative are borne by the initiative itself and/or the Structure that decided on its launch. Such costs include, by way of example, expenses for the purchase of software for text layout and image processing, for any outsourced services such as printing, distribution, and sale of the print edition, and for the payment of stamp duties for legal documentation (for example, communication of a change of the Editor-in-Chief of a journal registered with the Court).

3.10. Legal Deposit and Long-Term Conservation of Documents of Cultural Interest

UniTrento, in its function as a publishing entity, is required to comply with the Italian legislation on legal deposit of documents of cultural interest (Italian Law of 15th April 2004, no. 106). Concurrently with the fulfillment of this obligation, the University implements further measures aimed at facilitating the long-term conservation and public access to documents of cultural interest published by UniTrento, such as the donation of complimentary copies of each new print publication to the University libraries and the Trento municipal library, the storage of one copy of each new print publication at the Scientific Publications Office, and the joining to Magazzini Digitali, an Italian national service for the long-term conservation and access to digital documents of cultural interest. For the fulfillment of legal obligations and complementary measures adopted by the University, each editorial initiative publishing works in print edition is required to send the Office a predefined quantity of complimentary copies of each new publication within 30 days from their date of circulation. The Office is required to communicate to the interested editorial initiatives, through dedicated pages of the Service Desk portal and/or the University website, the exact number of copies to be sent, depending on the type of work and the formal or informal agreements between the University and the depositary institutions.

3.11. Agreements with External Parties

Editorial initiatives have the possibility, through their reference Structure, to enter into agreements with external parties for services concerning portions of editorial activity that are not offered by the University (for example, printing, layout, distribution, and sale of print editions). Agreements that imply co-responsibility between UniTrento and other publishing entities (for example, co-publications) shall be approved and signed by the Rector. The Office provides technical advice on the content of such agreements.

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3.12. Editorial Brand

UniTrento's editorial brand graphically coincides with the University's brand and is reserved for the University's editorial activity. Works that do not fall within the types mentioned in paragraph 3.1 (for example, working papers and technical reports, which lack any form of scientific assessment) may be published by the affiliated Structure, using the Structure's brand as defined by the University's Coordinated Identity Manual.

3.13. Support and Consultancy from the Office

The support and consultancy provided by the Office are reserved for editorial initiatives publishing works that fall within the types mentioned in paragraph 3.1. The services offered by the Office to editorial initiatives are detailed in section 4 of this document.

3.14. Harmonization of the Structures' Regulations about the Editorial Activity with the Guidelines

Each Structure that has adopted its own regulations concerning publications that are included in the University's editorial activity is required to make any necessary corrections so that the provisions contained therein do not conflict with what is established by these Guidelines, and shall always notify the Office of any changes to the aforementioned regulations.

4. DUTIES OF THE SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS OFFICE

The Office supports the University's editorial activity within the scopes, methods, and terms described in the following part of this document.

4.1. Coordination of the Editorial Initiatives

The Office's objective is to fully implement UniTrento's publishing policies (as per section 3), strengthening the editorial brand through the valorization of all initiatives, and working to ensure that each editorial initiative reaches or maintains the highest quality standards.

The Office offers consultancy and support to editorial initiatives for enhancing dissemination and indexing, for defining the quality and timing of their editorial processes, and for complying with ethical and scientific standards.

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The Office provides information on copyright management to all editorial initiatives and prospective authors, making available the relevant forms also through the Service Desk portal.

The Office promotes ways of collaboration and sharing of best practices among the managers of the different initiatives.

4.2. Publishing Platforms for Open Access Digital Editions

The Office ensures each editorial initiative access to one of the University's open access publishing platforms, as indicated in paragraph 3.5.

The Office has exclusive competence over the TESeO platform and manages its ordinary operation.

As site manager, the Office:

- defines the layout and content of the homepage and other website pages that do not refer to a specific editorial initiative;
- performs a basic configuration of the new initiatives' websites and provides their technical contact persons with access credentials to the platform and instructions on how to complete the configuration and on the general functioning of the platform;
- after verifying the completion of the configuration, puts the websites of new initiatives online;
- periodically checks the content of each initiative's website and reports any problems to the technical contact person, urging their intervention;
- intervenes on the content, settings, and published works on an initiative's website only upon explicit request from the technical contact person, while reserving the right to intervene without authorization to resolve problems that fall under the publisher's responsibility (e.g., interventions on plugins for the issuance and registration of DOIs; temporary obscuring of specific content following notification of infringements of University regulations);
- in case of serious infringements by an editorial initiative, takes its website offline as a temporary and transient measure, as provided in paragraph 3.8;
- allows the National Central Library of Florence to harvest platform content for the Magazzini Digitali project, as per paragraph 3.10;
- periodically extracts statistics on platform and resource access for monitoring activities, as per paragraph 4.9.

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As the sole interlocutor of the site administrator, the Office:

- forwards requests for intervention following reports of platform malfunctions received from the editorial initiatives;
- on behalf of the Directorate of IT and Library Services, forwards communications, requests, and documents relating to the domain <https://teseo.unitn.it/> (e.g., security certificates) and IT management;
- executes binding requests regarding software updates and maintenance, intervening on the platform directly and/or by delegating the contact persons of the interested initiatives.

The Office has non-exclusive competence over the use of the IRIS platform and shall request any relevant intervention from the Research Products Office. The Office is the only entity authorized to request the publication in IRIS of the full texts of books published by UniTrento.

4.3. Start of New Editorial Initiatives

The Office includes new editorial initiatives, falling within the types mentioned in paragraph 3.1, in the University's editorial activity, subject to approval of the relevant Structure, and oversees their launch. An initiative is deemed active after the publication of the first journal issue or book and the consequent assignment of an ISSN code (in the case of journals or books series), or after the successful publication of the individual work (in the case of single books).

The Office provides consultancy and support to the proposer of a new initiative in defining the various aspects of the editorial project, which will be submitted for approval to its Structure. The project comprises: the type of content and the consequent method of content quality assessment, the bodies and individuals responsible for the initiative, the securing of necessary economic and human resources, the author guidelines, and the graphic design. The Office provides informational materials regarding peer review models, the publishing platforms used by UniTrento, copyright management, the Creative Commons licenses, the necessary licenses to publish, and the requirements that allow for the bibliographic recognition of an initiative as published by UniTrento, and for its classification and indexing.

The Office provides support in completing the form for starting a new editorial initiative (*Scheda dell'iniziativa editoriale*, as per paragraph 3.2).

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The proposer will notify the Office about the reference Structure's approval of the start of a new initiative through the Service Desk portal.

The Office provides consultancy and support to the Editorial Team of the approved editorial initiative until the successful publication of the first (or sole) work through a specific procedure available on the Service Desk portal, according to the methods illustrated in paragraph 4.4. For journals published in TESeO, the Office performs a basic configuration of the initiative's website, and provides the technical contact person with access credentials to the publishing platform and instructions for its use (see paragraph 4.2 for details). Once the configuration of the website is completed, the Office puts it online.

For continuous editorial initiatives, after the successful publication of the first work, the Office carries out the procedure for assigning an ISSN code (see paragraph 4.5); in the case of journals, the Office also communicates their start to the Register of Communication Operators (see paragraph 4.6). Subsequently, the Office continues to provide consultancy and support to the initiative as provided in paragraph 4.1.

4.4. Publication

All initiatives falling within the University's editorial activity are granted the possibility of publishing their works on the open access platforms mentioned in paragraph 4.2.

The Office carries out the publication of a work at the request of the relevant initiative's Editorial Team. The request shall be submitted to the Office through a specific procedure available on the Service Desk portal, attaching the definitive version of the work; this request also entails the assignment of appropriate bibliographic identification codes (ISBNs and, only for books published in IRIS, DOIs) to the work. By sending the request, the Editorial Team certifies that the work has undergone a scientific assessment and declares that all the license to publish forms have been collected and archived on behalf of the publisher, as per paragraph 3.7.

The Office accepts the publication request after verifying the publication requirements and the formal quality of the work. This process includes verifying the work's conformity with the graphic design, the consistent application of author guidelines, the orthographic correctness of the texts, as well as the correct application of title page and colophon templates and all other aspects that guarantee the work's recognizability as published by UniTrento. The Office has the right to request the Editorial Team to make all necessary modifications, failing which the work will not be published.

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Once all requested modifications have been made, the Office assigns the bibliographic identification codes provided in paragraph 3.6; when necessary, it requests the Editorial Team to insert them in the work's copyright page before publication.

The Office may suspend online access to already-published works to protect the publisher, as detailed in paragraph 3.8.

4.5. Purchase and Assignment of Bibliographic Identification Codes

The Office is responsible for the purchase of ISBN and ISSN codes on behalf of the University and guarantees the assignment of ISBN, ISSN, and DOI codes to works falling within the University's editorial activity, according to the criteria defined in paragraph 3.6.

4.6. Fulfillment of Journal Registration Obligations and Communication of Relevant Changes

The Office is required to promptly communicate to the Rector, or to the person delegated by them to operate on the electronic system of the Register of Communication Operators (ROC), all information necessary for the registration with the ROC of a new journal or informational periodical published by UniTrento. Registration is considered an integral part of the launching of a new journal, as indicated in paragraph 4.3, and shall be carried out within thirty days from the publication of the first issue.

Each editorial initiative has the responsibility (see paragraph 3.8) to promptly communicate to the Office any suspension or cessation of a journal, as well as any changes to the data communicated to the ROC during the registration of the publication:

- journal title;
- distribution format(s);
- identification data of the registration of the journal with the Court, where applicable;
- periodicity;
- start date of publication;
- website where the digital edition of the journal is published;
- name and fiscal code of the Editor-in-Chief.

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The Office, in turn, has the responsibility to communicate annually to the Rector, or to the person delegated by them, any changes reported by the editorial initiatives, in order to include them in the annual communication to the ROC, which UniTrento shall obligatorily make by July 31st of each year.

If changes relating to the title, periodicity, or Editor-in-Chief affect a UniTrento journal previously registered with the Court, the Editor-in-Chief is obliged to communicate them to the same Court, submitting formal documentation that shall also be signed by the Rector, as owner and publisher of the journal. In these cases, the Editor-in-Chief shall prepare the required documentation, personally or by delegation, and submit it to the Office; in turn, the Office shall verify the accuracy of the data, forward to the Rector the documents requiring their signature, and verify their successful transmission to the Court by the editorial initiative.

4.7. Fulfillment of Obligations and Internal Provisions Regarding the Long-Term

Conservation of Documents of Cultural Interest

The Office has exclusive responsibility for fulfilling the legal deposit obligations for print editions published by UniTrento and for implementing the other measures (referred to in paragraph 3.10) to facilitate the long-term conservation and access to the University's publications.

For the fulfillment of legal obligations and other measures adopted by the University, the Office communicates to the relevant editorial initiatives, through specific pages of the Service Desk portal and/or the University website, the exact number of print copies required for each type of work, and monitors the actual receipt of the same within the foreseen terms.

The Office is UniTrento's contact person for the Magazzini Digitali project, an Italian national service for the long-term conservation and access to digital documents of cultural interest

4.8. Support for Indexing and Classification

Upon request from the editorial initiatives, the Office offers consultancy and support for applying for indexing in bibliographic, citation, and disciplinary databases, as well as for classification of journals in non-bibliometric areas for the purpose of National Scientific Qualification. The submission of the application is the responsibility of the editorial initiative; only in cases where the application shall come directly from the publisher, the Office

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will submit it on behalf of the initiative. In any case, responsibility for the correctness of the data communicated in the application lies with the editorial initiative.

4.9. Monitoring and Statistics on the Editorial Activity

The Office provides, upon request, statistical data on the University's editorial activity for internal surveys and for external institutional surveys (ISTAT statistics on publications, Italian monitoring on Open Access).

4.10. Promotion of the Editorial Brand

The Office contributes to the promotion of the editorial brand by participating in trade fairs, conferences, and dedicated meetings where to showcase the University's editorial activity.

4.11. Relationships with Other Academic Publishers

The Office maintains relationships with other academic publishers, both Italian and international, also by participating in collaborative projects in order to share experiences, expertise, and best practices.

4.12. Open Science Commission

The Office regularly participates in the work of the Open Science Commission through its own representative, who is responsible for coordinating the working group concerning the University's editorial activity.

4.13. Service Desk portal

The Office shares and updates information, instructions and procedures related to the provision of editorial services on the University's Service Desk portal.